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Tidal Energy Resource Assessment at the Atlantic Marine Energy Center Tidal Energy Test Site

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Abstract

An easy-to-access and well-understood tidal energy test facility has been developed by the Atlantic Marine Energy Center (AMEC), to help progress the field of tidal energy conversion towards commercial feasibility and to lower the barrier of entry for turbine developers. The AMEC tidal energy test site is located at Memorial Bridge in Portsmouth, NH, in the Piscataqua River of the Great Bay Estuarine System, and allows researchers and developers to test their tidal energy converters (TECs) in a real, energetic tidal flow. This work will provide a summary of the available tidal energy resource for any device to be tested at AMEC's tidal energy test site, along with constraints to be placed on these devices.

Keywords: Tidal Energy; Resource Characterization;

1. Introduction

1.1. Motivation

The deterministic nature of the tides allows predictions of the tidal energy resource at specific locations. In the pursuit of a suitable location for a TEC deployment, nationwide resource surveys can be a helpful starting point for developers [1]. However, it is known that hydrodynamic conditions can change drastically over short distances [2]. Additionally, turbulence can lead to a significant increase in the available tidal energy resource [3]. Therefore, a local assessment needs to be performed, since the provided spatial and temporal resolution of a larger-scale survey or simulation will not be adequate to site a TEC or an array of TECs. The aim of this work is to accurately assess the tidal energy resource at the AMEC Tidal Energy Test Site and compare to and augment previous tidal energy resource assessments at the site [4] [5] [6], to aid in the scaling of any prototype-scale devices up to field-scale, and to validate and verify relevant numerical models. To accomplish this, the 1) mean inflow current and 2) the turbulent characteristics of the flow across the turbine deployment, or energy extraction plane (EEP) plane must be understood.

Typically, acoustic Doppler current profilers (ADCPs) are used for tidal resource assessment. However, ADCPs alone do not commonly offer the temporal or spatial resolution necessary to properly evaluate the tidal energy resource at the EEP scale or blade scale fluctuations that can have a significant impact on dynamic loading and energy capture. The typical sampling rate of an ADCP is too low to capture these fluctuations. By design, an acoustic Doppler velocimeter (ADV) has a much higher sample rate (O~10 Hz) than an ADCP (O~1 Hz), and a much greater spatial resolution (O~1 cm³ compared to O~1 m³). By utilizing an ADV for a resource characterization, some of the limitations of an ADCP are circumvented [7]. However, some limitations must be accepted, such as obtaining only a quasi-point measurement. The accurate characterization of turbulence must be completed with an ADV; however, the small sampling volume is not sufficient to gather inflow velocity data over an entire EEP. An ADCP measures the spatially and temporally averaged velocity within bins over some distance from the ADCP, creating an inflow velocity

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profile over the area of interest. By using ADVs and ADCPs together, both small-scale turbulence and mean inflow velocities over the EEP can be characterized simultaneously.

The tidal energy resource characterization at a test site for TECs is not only important for TEC developers and researchers, but it also informs design of infrastructure at the site (i.e., survivability of structures, maintenance cycles, etc.). This work aims to improve the understanding of the available resource at the Atlantic Marine Energy Center Tidal Energy Test Site through a concurrent, long-term ADCP and ADV survey at the TEC deployment location.

Nomenclature

AMEC	Atlantic Marine Energy Center
ADCP	Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler
ADV	Acoustic Doppler Velocimeter
NSF	National Science Foundation
NHDOT	New Hampshire Department of Transportation
EEP	Energy Extraction Plane
TDP	Turbine Deployment Platform
TEC	Tidal Energy Converter
UNH	University of New Hampshire

1.2. Test Site Description

The AMEC Tidal Energy Test Site is located at Memorial Bridge in the Piscataqua River of the Great Bay estuarine system (Figure 1), one of the most energetic tidal estuaries on the East Coast of the United States. The site was first developed under the NSF-funded “Living Bridge” project at the Memorial Bridge in Portsmouth, NH [8].

Figure 1: Location of the UNH-AMEC tidal energy test site in Portsmouth, NH [9]

UNH developed and deployed a turbine deployment platform (TDP) moored to the Memorial Bridge to facilitate device deployment and testing at the site (Figure 2). The TDP is a pontoon-style floating platform capable of deploying TECs up to approximately 3 meters in diameter through a moonpool in the center of a steel frame.

Figure 2: The UNH-AMEC tidal deployment platform (TDP) with an example of a tidal energy conversion device (here, a 2.5 m diameter axial-flow turbine) deployed through the moonpool of the platform.

2. Methods

2.1. Instrumentation

The mean inflow current velocity will be measured with two Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (ADCPs). The instruments will both be bottom-facing and deployed ~6 meters (about twice the diameter of suitable TECs) up- and down-stream of the energy extraction plane (EEP) at approximately 0.4 meters depth (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Location of ADCPs (blue circles) and ADVs (orange squares) on the TDP with the EEP highlighted.

The velocity will be averaged and reported in two-minute ensembles as inflow on both the ebb and flood tides. The measurements of velocity will serve as an estimate of the mean energy density at the EEP and help to inform turbine developers of the range of devices that could be tested in this location. The turbulent characteristics of the flow will

be measured using Acoustic Doppler Velocimeters (ADVs). The ADV instruments will be deployed less than 1 meter away from the EEP with sampling volumes at a depth of approximately 2 meters, which would be the approximate hub height of a 2.5m diameter axial flow turbine (Figure 3). Three ADVs will be deployed across the EEP to resolve the directionality/uniformity of the flow. The instantaneous velocity will be measured with a sampling rate of 64 Hz to adequately resolve the relevant-scale turbulent structures for energy capture and hydrodynamic loading.

2.2. Analysis

The average energy density of the flow at the test site will be calculated using ensemble-averaged velocity data collected with ADCP at the bow and stern of the TDP. The ensemble averaging time will be varied from 1 to 15 minutes to examine the effect of averaging time on the tidal energy resource. An example of ADCP data collected from the TDP in Fall 2017 is shown in Figure 4. The velocity measurements on the bow and stern show good agreement on the flood tide (positive velocity), while there is a significant deviation for the stern ADCP for part of the ebb tide due to a shear layer originating from the bridge pier. The velocity change of over 1 m/s between the bow and stern of the TDP (~15 m) highlights the need for velocity measurements at the EEP to accurately report the available energy.

Figure 4: Example of tidal current magnitude as measured by ADCPs (ADCP1 is on the stern of the TDP, ADCP 2 is on the bow) in 2-minute ensemble averages at 1.4 m depth [6]

The energy density excursions due to turbulence will be estimated using the instantaneous velocity as measured by ADVs near the EEP. Combined with the average energy density, estimations will be made of the total energy density available for conversion, as well as the total loading on any device deployed at this location. Additionally, relevant turbulent statistics (integral timescales, length-scales, TKE, etc.) will be calculated, along with an estimation of the flow directionality near the EEP. Figure 5 shows an example of ADV velocity data collected during a Perigean spring tide in Fall 2021 at the bow of the platform, showing that tidal current can locally exceed 3 m/s, which is important for design considerations.

Figure 5: Current magnitude as recorded by an ADV sampling at 16 Hz on the bow of the platform at 1.6 m depth [10].

3. Summary

The AMEC Tidal Energy Test Site is located at Memorial Bridge in Portsmouth, NH in the Piscataqua River of the Great Bay estuarine system. A tidal energy resource characterization will be conducted at the test site to augment previous characterization efforts that will consist of a concurrent deployment of ADVs and ADCPs. This work will provide a summary of the available resource and relevant turbulence statistics, as well as design constraints to be placed on any device in the flow.

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